

Utilization and Perception of Library Users in the use of Electronic Resources: An Input towards Digitalization of COTT Library

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Abstract:- As Information and Communications Technology (ICT) has already become an integral aspect of an academic library, e-resources have also aided for wider and easier access of technical information. Relatively, the study aimed to assess the utilization and perception of college students, faculty, and staff in Camarines Norte State College – College of Trades and Technology (CNSC-COTT), a higher education institution in the province of Camarines Norte, Philippines in the use of e-resources which will be a basis for inputs towards its digitalization. A quantitative research design was used to which a survey was deployed via google forms. The consolidated data shows that 82% of the respondents were already aware of the e-resources provided by the library. However, considerations may still be taken into accounts to improve statistical results such as strengthening information dissemination, improvement of the internet subscription and likewise, improve the skills of the clientele when it comes to using the facilities. Likewise, it was also noted that among the respondents, faculty members were the most satisfied with a mean score of 4.56 whereas students and staff were at a satisfactory level. In determining the satisfaction level of the respondents, demographics of the respondents were taken into consideration and determined its influence. Relatively, it was noted that role of the respondent (be it student, faculty, or staff) and the year level of the respondents has great influence in the determination of satisfaction level over the sex of the respondents. Statistics show that p value for both variables was at -0.158 and -0.088 that was greater than ($\alpha = 0.05$) validating the influence of the said variables.

Keywords:- Library resources, ICT, E-resources, descriptive research, research culture, Bicol, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Science fiction books and movies had already depicted that the world will be moving towards a revolutionized way of doing things. From the first machine that started the Industrial Revolution in 1760 to the start of digitalization and automation through electronics and computers in 1900s, the world has indeed come a long way now. We were now endeavoring in the 4th Industrial Revolution where the age of digitalization has come to a more mature portrayal: where virtual and augmented reality was now part of the human interaction with the society. As such, the education sector in the Philippines, though being a

third world country, was striving to cope with these changes.

One aspect to which the education was working on with was the repository of knowledge. In the earlier days, physical libraries were home to thousands of knowledges that were hidden in each page of the books, waiting to be read. This had been the go-to place for students, academicians, and researchers alike as it fosters all the necessary information to a particular knowledge that needs to be sought. From general information to literary books, to a more specific scientific breakthroughs that were documented. And with the age of digitalization and the wide range to which the world-wide-web can reach, human was being more dependent with digital platforms as it provides a more convenient way of accessing information. Likewise, the library as an information provider seeks to ensure that the providing reliable and up-to-date information to its users were still managed.

As such, most libraries had tried to incorporate the four elements of competitive design into their operations: quality, innovation, efficiency and responsive to patron needs (Moran & Morner, 2018) to meet the fast changes in the library management. For example, the use of Cloud infrastructure in providing a vast warehouse for internet-accessible resources had already proven to be an advantage to eliminate the problem on physical weeding of obsolete books that were no longer within the range of time to which references should be stored in a physical set-up (Kehoe, Patil, Abbeel, & Goldberg, 2014). Likewise, the use of such infrastructure for databases and data repository had been a great advantage in stand-alone robotics and automation systems. However, the cost to which such infrastructure may be implemented in State Colleges and Universities in the Philippines was somewhat pricey. Wiley's, and international e-resources site, online access to journals as of 2022 shows that the average subscription to was at \$240.00 dollars likewise, The Modern Teacher Magazine incur an average estimated cost of Php 1, 200.00 for a subscription to available e-resources.

As such, library consortiums were established in the country. Results of related studies had proven that the academic library consortia offering open access to students and academicians alike plays a significant role in the development of libraries. Furthermore, the success evident among consortia were undeniable due to the important roles played by technology in open resource sharing (Fresnido & Yap, 2014).

Although it was a great opportunity to incorporate digitalization in the library resources, there were still challenges experienced, particularly in the patron side. Chandel in 2012 had already enumerated the possible challenges and opportunities of e-resources (Chandel & Saikia, 2012). According to them, among the challenges that affects the utilization in e-resources were impact of e-resources to user behavior, collection development, cost and purchasing of e-resources and establishment of consortia, archival problem, and management issues. Similarly, Li et.al also finds key points that needs to be further studied as he believed that it would pose a threat and crisis in the management of library e-resources in the future. Among of which were the resource delivery, utilization of the existing resources, the social recognition to which this new venture was perceived by the patrons and finally, the change in thinking of the existing library staff (Li, Jiao, Zhang, & Xu, 2019). Relatively, as identified by Roman et.al in 2020, three factors which affects the utilization of e-library, particularly Gale E-Resources, are: Awareness, Usefulness and Challenges (Roman, et al., 2020). Relatively, the low utilization rate result of student use of e-resources was greatly influenced by the lack of awareness and technical knowledge. Another finding of the study shows that although students were aware of the existence of the online resource, they were not particularly aware of what resources were provided by the library.

The researcher would like to assess the utilization, perception and challenges faced by the students, instructors, and staff of the CNSC-COTT in using the different library databases subscribed by the institution: IG Publishing, McGraw-Hill Access Engineering, GALE (Infotrac) and Press Reader in the four dimensions of the competitive design of Library and Information Center Management. The information collected in this study will be a basis for an intervention that the Campus Library may offer to the clientele for the betterment of the services provided.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The study employed a quantitative approach in evaluating the different parameters in determining the utilization and perception of library users in the use of electronic resources, which collectively aims to provide inputs in the digitalization of the College of Trades and Technology Library.

B. Population

The population of the study constitutes the 819 students enrolled in the CNSC-COTT for the 1st Semester of A.Y. 2022-2023 and the 40 faculty and staff that were employed in the same semester. A sample size of 273 from the total population was determined using Slovin's. Figure 1 below represents the number of respondents:

Table 1: Population and sample

Group	Total Number	%	Sample Size
BSIT-AT	87	10%	28
BSIT-CT	115	13%	37
BSIT-ETT	74	9%	24
BSIT-ELT	92	11%	29
BTVTE-AT	69	8%	22
BTVTE-ET	102	12%	32
BTVTE-FSM	167	19%	53
BTVTE-FGT	113	13%	36
Faculty	30	3%	10
Staff	10	1%	3
TOTAL	859	100%	273

C. Data Collection and Instrument

Using a survey questionnaire that was developed via google forms, random convenience sampling method was conducted to collect necessary data for the study which includes:

➤ Demographic profile of the respondents

- Sex
- Role
- Year level (for students)

➤ The perception of patrons in the use of e-resources in terms of:

- Awareness of e-resources
- Preference of using e-resources
- Difficulties in accessing e-resources.

➤ Utilization of e-resources of the library users in terms of:

- Frequency of using e-resources
- Purpose of using e-resources
- Methods of learning e-resources usage skills
- Location of accessing e-resources
- Linking patterns of e-resources
- Use patterns of e-resources
- Format of e-resources used.

Data gathering runs from the approval of the study on July 2022 up to November 2022. At this point, the College had already shifted from the limited face to face modality towards full implementation of face-to-face, thus more respondents were able to take part in the study. The survey questionnaire was forwarded to the respondents through links on any available platforms which was not limited to FB Messenger accounts and e-mail addresses of the target respondents. Also, an informed consent was attached to the

survey questionnaire to secure approval and to ensure that the respondents were aware of the proceedings of the any information derived from the said survey.

D. Data Analysis

The following were statistical treatments used to induce necessary information out of the collected data:

- *Percentage was used to describe the demographics of the respondents in terms of sex, role, and the year level for the students. Likewise, the following parameters were also analyzed using percentage concept:*
- Difficulties in accessing e-resources.

- Purposes when accessing e-resources.
- E-resources formats used.
- *Frequency distribution was used to determine the following parameters:*
- Awareness on e-resources
- Kind of e-resources
- Preference on e-resources
- Frequency of using e-resources
- *Mean score was used for the Satisfaction Level of respondents as follow:*

Table 2: Likert Scale

Numerical Scale	Descriptive Rating
5.0	Very Satisfactory
4.0	Satisfactory
3.0	Neutral or Acceptable
2.0	Unsatisfactory
1.0	Highly unsatisfactory

Data results will be interpreted as follows:

Table 3: Mean Score Interpretation

Numerical Scale	Descriptive Rating
4.51 - 5.00	Very Satisfactory
3.51 - 4.50	Satisfactory
2.51 - 3.50	Neutral or Acceptable
1.51 - 2.50	Unsatisfactory
1.00 - 1.50	Highly unsatisfactory

- *Regression analysis whether sex and roles were predictors for the satisfaction level.*

E. Ethical Protocols

All respondents signed an agreement with the institution. All data collected were treated with strict confidentiality based on the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and the Research Manual of the CNSC.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially, the study mapped the demographics of the respondents based on the expected responses. As a result, Table 4 and 5 represents the distribution of respondents per parameters.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by Sex

Criteria	No.	%
Male	150	41%
Female	214	59%
TOTAL	364	100%

The data gathering proved that out 273 sample size determined through Slovin computation of sample size, an increase of 33.33% was noted from the expected responses. Relatively, it was also noted that among that majority of the respondents were female at 59% against the 41% respondents from male.

On the other hand, the distribution of respondents according to their role in the College (Student, Faculty, and Staff) showed that the required number of respondents were slightly met. Student and Staff required number of responses have been met based on the percentage requirements. However, it was noted that the faculty responses were unmet with a lack of 1. However, the slight difference in the number of respondents per the role does

not affect the overall results of the study as the direct clientele of the library services were the students and their inputs were highly regarded in this study.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents by Role

Criteria	No.	%	Remarks
Student	353	97%	Met
Faculty	9	2%	Unmet
Staff	2	1%	Met
TOTAL	362	100%	

Categories of student respondents were also regarded in this study. Based on Figure 1, student respondents were categorized into year levels. The data presented in the said figure will be significant in the determination of the influence of the demographic profiles of the respondents,

particularly the students in the satisfaction level of the use of e-resources.

Based on Figure 1, majority of the respondents were collected from first year students. Relatively, 4th year students have the least responses as they were not available at the time of the data gathering due to their internship.

Fig. 1: Distribution of Student Respondents by Year Level

Perception as defined by the American Psychological Association (APA) was a process to which an individual was becoming aware of objects, relationships, and events through the different senses (Cherry, 2022). With this definition, the study employed several parameters to determine the perception of the clientele of COTT Library in the use of e-resources as the new normal was already in place.

In terms of awareness on e-library resources that the COTT Library offers, statistics shows that 82% out of 364 responses were aware that the COTT Library has e-resources for the variety of purposes. Likewise, only 18% were not aware of this. The numbers as reflected in Table 6 shows that the clientele of COTT were well versed with the services offered by the office and fully aware of the electronic resources that were being offered for a variety of purposes.

Table 6: Awareness on Library E-Resources of COTT Library

Criteria	No.	%
YES	300	82%
NO	64	18%
TOTAL	364	100%

Relative to this, the respondents were asked of their preferred e-resources. Based on the gathered data, it was noted that the respondents prefer to use e-books out of the

subscriptions offered by COTT. Figure 2 below reflects the preferences of the 300 respondents of the study who agreed to be aware of the resource’s offerings:

Fig. 2: Preferred E-Resources

64% of the total 300 respondents all agreed to prefer e-books among other e-resources. Commonly, e-books or electronic books were electronic copies of published books. These were preferred to by most students and faculty as it becomes a reference material in their subjects. Either way, it can be accessed through multiple devices. Furthermore, its versatility allows students to download the file into storage drives or even in their android phones.

On the contrary, it was noted that only 7% agreed to prefer magazines. Although magazines provide latest trends among in the field of specialization with articles that were periodically updated, most of the clientele prefer e-books since it serves as reference books for their studies.

Although e-resources were available in the COTT Library, several limitations were still prevalent. In terms of accessibility and ease of use, the respondents were also

asked of commonly experienced difficulties as it will serve as basis for the development of opportunities for improvements. Based on the collected data, the most prevailing difficulties experienced by the clientele was the unstable internet connection/ slow internet speed to which the library was currently subscribed to. 21% of the respondents all agreed that this was the major difficulty they experienced when accessing e-resources. This was then followed by the limited number of e-resources that was available for the subject matter. About 19% of the respondents relatively experienced these difficulties. Although, the most prevailing issues identified were more on the technical aspect of the e-resources, a percentage of the respondents still consider other factors including information dissemination, knowledge, and technical assistance as among the difficulties they experience. To summarize, Table 7 reflects the consolidated data.

Table 7: Difficulties in accessing E-Resources

Criteria	No.	%
Limited E-Resources available in my subjects	124	19%
Coverage on E-Resources was not suited to my research area	35	5%
Lack of assistance provided by the library staff	26	4%
Lack of training/ no orientation	27	4%
Time consuming	44	7%
Unstable internet connection/slow internet speed	131	21%
Struggle in finding related information	67	10%
Limited access to a computer terminal	51	8%
Lack of IT knowledge to effectively use the services	49	8%
Using electronic resources often distracts me from doing other works	39	6%
budget to access e-resources	46	7%
TOTAL	639	100%

Another aspect of this study was to describe how the library e-resources were utilized by the clientele from the frequency of use to the formats commonly used. As such the following data were presented to summarize the utilization of e-resources at COTT.

Based on the tabulated data, majority of the respondents agreed to have used e-resources of COTT Library for once a week. This constitutes to 34% of the respondents. Whereas 23% agreed to have used it once every month. About 22 out of 300 responded to have never used e-resources although they were aware of the service. To summarize, Table 8 below was presented.

Table 8: Frequency of E-Resources Use

Criteria	No.	%
Daily	51	17%
Once a Week	102	34%
Twice a Week	57	19%
Once a Month	68	23%
Never	22	7%
TOTAL	300	100%

In relation to the frequency of use, the purpose of using e-resources was also measured. This includes parameters that pertain to the use of e-resources for both academic and entertainment purposes. As such, the results showed that 35% use e-resources for answering assignments and homework tasked by instructors. Since majority of the e-books becomes references for relevant subjects, it becomes sources of information to answer the tasks given.

Information dissemination and orientation programs were important to ensure that awareness of the services, particularly the e-resources were well informed to the prospective clientele. As such, the measure of how the clientele become aware of the e-resources was measured. Likewise, this measure provides an insight as to how effective the services of the library in information dissemination.

The data consolidated reflects that majority of the respondents become aware of the e-resources provision of COTT library through orientation/re-orientation program provided by the library. This includes the utilization and incorporation of segments for student orientation and re-orientation program to deliver and inform the clientele of services offered including access to e-resources. Statistics shows that 49% of the respondents agreed to have known this service through the said information dissemination program. Likewise, the use of Facebook page as a platform for information dissemination also shows effectiveness as 19% of the respondents agreed to have known e-resources as posted in the official Facebook page of the COTT Library. Thus, this implies the existing strategies for information dissemination was effective.

Table 9 reflects the statistics of information dissemination about the e-resources of COTT Library.

Table 9: Information Dissemination Strategies of COTT Library

Criteria	No.	%
orientation/re-orientation on accessing electronic resources provided by the library	147	49%
bulletin board and display of the library	55	18%
library Facebook page	57	19%
others	41	14%
TOTAL	300	100%

E-Resources were generally available in devices and likewise, in all locations if credentials were used. Relatively, to determine the location patterns to which e-resources were accessed, a measure of access points was included. This serves as a basis to determine whether the current facilities as well as the infrastructure of the COTT

library was enough to sustain the need of accessing e-resources.

Table 10 below reflects the location spots to which e-resources were accessed.

Table 10: Access Points of E-Resources

Criteria	No.	%
boarding house/home	0	0%
college library	223	92%
computer laboratory	8	3%
computer shops	12	5%
others	0	0%
TOTAL	243	100%

As reflected in Table 8, most of the respondent's accessed e-resources in the College Library despite the information that the current internet subscription of the library was not enough to sustain the needs of the clients. 92% agreed with this notion, whereas 5% agreed to access the resources in computer shops.

On the other hand, the linking pattern was the determination to which e-resources were accessed. This idea provides insights as to how knowledgeable and skillful the clientele were in accessing the e-resources. This includes accessing links in different areas of the virtual world. As such, Table 9 below reflects the linking patterns by the clientele:

Table 11: Linking patterns

Criteria	No.	%
Links through library websites	141	47%
Links through publisher's website	21	7%
Links through search engines	40	13%
Links through E-Resources websites	71	24%
others	27	9%
TOTAL	300	100%

The table shows that most of the respondents use the library website or the official Facebook page to access the links of the e-resources. 141 or 47% out of 300 respondents agreed with this notion. Whereas only a handful agreed to have used the links on the publisher’s website and other means. This could be an avenue to allow students a variety of access to available e-resources.

Likewise, when asked how the e-resources contents were utilized, most of the respondents agreed to have

downloaded the e-resources to a storage device for their consumption. 44% out of 300 agreed to this and that this was used most of the time as it allows them to review and read the contents of the e-resources without the use of the internet. Others on the other hand state that printouts and screenshots of the e-resource contents were utilized for much easier access and review of the contents. To summarize this notion, Figure 3 was presented below:

Fig. 3: Utilization of E-Resources Contents

Lastly, as a basis for improvements for the current e-resources, the study also takes into consideration the most used format of e-resources. This includes electronic formats of documents and resources such as Hypertext Markup

Language (HTML), PDF, video, audio, and other relevant formats. As such, Table 12 below summarizes the most used e-resources format.

Table 12: Format of E-Resources

Criteria	No.	%
HTML	44	18%
PDF	188	76%
Video	58	24%
Audio	18	7%
PPTX	60	24%
Word Document	146	59%
Spreadsheet	12	5%
Others	22	9%
TOTAL	246	100%

Based on the table, it was noted that the majority agreed to use PDF as the most frequency used format at 76%. Aside from the fact that the contents of e-resources were compressed in a single file, it was easy to download and does not carry too much memory of a device. This was followed by word documents with 59% responses. Word documents were downloadable and easy to edit.

Submissions via online usually were in the form of word documents to allow comments and remarks to be made.

In summary, the general mean score to represent the satisfaction level of the clientele relative to the e-resources services provided by the COTT Library was 4.14 which was equivalent to Satisfactory. Relatively, to determine the satisfactory level among the demographics, Table 13 was presented below:

Table 13: Satisfaction Level

Variables		Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
<i>Sex</i>			
Male		4.06	Satisfactory
Female		4.19	Satisfactory
	<i>n=</i> 300		
<i>Role</i>			
Student		4.13	Satisfactory
Faculty		4.56	Very Satisfactory
Staff		4.00	Satisfactory
	<i>n=</i> 300		
<i>Student Year Level</i>			
1st Year		4.14	Satisfactory
2nd Year		4.12	Satisfactory
3rd Year		4.00	Satisfactory
4th Year		4.21	Satisfactory
	<i>n=</i> 291		

As Table 13 presented, although both sexes were satisfied with the provisions and services of e-resources in COTT library, it was also noted that female were slightly more satisfied than males at a difference of 0.13 in the mean scores. Relatively, faculty members were very much satisfied with the services. A mean score of 4.56, equivalent to very satisfactory, was noted. Furthermore, the statistics also show that both students and staff were also satisfied with the e-resources although the level was not as high as that among the faculty.

Finally, among the student year levels, although all of them were at a satisfactory level, it was noted that a 4th year student who responded to the survey conducted was more satisfied than other year levels. This may be attributed to the fact that they had already experienced and had been using e-resources much longer than other year levels.

Relative to this, it was also noted that the 1st year students rank 2nd with the most satisfied respondents. This shows that even though they only had a few months of academic residency in the college, they appreciate the e-resources of the college.

The use of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was used whether the demographics of the respondents would have significant influence as to the satisfaction level on the e-resources used. Relatively, it was noted that the model summary reflects an $R^2 = 0.013$ which reflects a low estimate for the dependent variable. This further implies that the independent variables identified in the model equation (sex, role, and year level) cannot provide good explanation as to the determination of the dependent variable (satisfaction level).

Table 14: Model Summary

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	RMSE
0.114	0.013	0.003	0.712

Table 15: Analysis of Variance

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F	P
Regression:	1.974	3	0.658	1.297	0.276
Residual:	150.146	296	0.507		
Total	152.120	299			

Relatively, the Analysis of variance also reflects $P = 0.276$ at an alpha level ($\alpha = 0.05$). The value shows that it was above the α value meaning, it was not significant, thus,

we reject the null hypothesis and accept that the sex, role, and year level has significant influence as the satisfaction level of clientele using e-resources in the library.

Table 16: Regression Coefficient

	Unstandardized (B)	Standardized Error (β)	t	P	Coefficient Interval
Sex	0.121	0.085	1.419	0.157	[-0.047, 0.290]
Role	0.286	0.225	1.268	0.206	[-0.158, 0.729]
Year Level	-0.008	0.040	-0.210	0.834	[-0.088, 0.071]
Intercept	3.663	0.253	14.497	<0.0001	[3.166, 4.160]

Finally, Table 16 above reflects the regression coefficients of each independent variable identified. Based on the Beta values (standardized error) $\beta = 0.225$, among the variables identified, the role of the respondents to the survey shows higher significance in the determination of the satisfaction level among clientele against the other variables: sex and year level. Relative role and year Level reflects a value that was greater than ($\alpha = 0.05$). Thus, the individual significance of the two variables can be used to assert that both variables have a strong relation towards the satisfaction level of the use of e-resources. However, sex reflects a value that was lower than ($\alpha = 0.05$) which means a significant value. Thus, the H_0 cannot be rejected which further implies that sex was not a determinant of the level of satisfaction for the use of e-resources in the CoTT Library.

IV. CONCLUSION

The library as an integral aspect of an academic institution houses knowledge that greatly supplements the teachings provided by individual instructors and professors. Likewise, these knowledge serves as a foundation for learning through self-dependency. Relative to this, the expansion of library holdings through the aid of the World Wide Web was a significant improvement particularly at the digital age as physical books were already replaced by electronic resources for two purposes: (a) ease of access and (b) vast network of fields. This allows students and researchers to be able to gather data at a click of the finger.

The inputs from the data collection and analysis reflects several points for improvement of the COTT library in the aspect of digitalization. Since there was already a good establishment of the e-resources, it was noted that the 82% awareness level among the respondents was already significant. However, practice of information dissemination may still be considered to improve these statistics although the practice of inclusion of the provisions of the library services particularly in the use of e-resources during orientation/re-orientation of students, other strategies may also be considered to boost the awareness of the students. In addition, the library may also consider to subscribe to a more reliant internet connection as it was noted from the respondents that unstable internet connection or slow internet speed was one of the struggles identified in accessing e-resources furthermore, additional subscriptions to e-libraries, e-journals, e-magazines and e-newspapers can also be considered as the limited number e-resources available for specific subjects was also noted to be second in rank among the difficulties.

On the other hand, the utilization of e-resources, varied response was relatively reflected. The frequency of use reflects of at least once a week among the respondents which were commonly accessed in the campus library. The linking patterns of use was also noted to which 47% of the respondents all agreed to have used the links in the official

Facebook page of the COTT library download e-resources in pdf formats in supplement to the knowledge acquired in the classroom and relatively use this answer homework and tasks given by the instructor.

Overall, the satisfaction level of the respondents for the provision of e-resources in the library was at 4.14 which was equivalent to satisfactory. Furthermore, based on the statistical treatment, it also reflects that faculty members using e-resources were the most satisfied with the services as the mean score of their satisfaction level was at 4.56 equivalent to very satisfactory.

Relatively, determining the influence of the demographics towards the determination of the satisfaction level also shows that both the role of the respondents as well as the year level of the students has great significance to the determination of satisfaction level, on the contrary, sex of the respondents was relatively not significant. Thus, when conduct of improvements to the digitalization of COTT Library, role and the year level of the clientele would be a basis for any inputs of improvement.

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